

Neo-Vaishnavite Movement: Cultural and Religious Renaissance and its Impact on the Assamese Society

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Abstract

The Neo-Vaishnavite movement emerged as a distinct religious tradition in Assam under the aegis of the saint-scholar Srimanta Sankardeva. Neo-Vaishnavism or the 'Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma' was propagated in Assam in the 15th and 16th century as a part of a pan-Indian Bhakti movement which challenged the orthodox religious practices of the time. In this context, this paper will try to historically trace the evolution and growth of the neo-vaishnavite sect in Assam and its role in bringing a socio-cultural and religious revolution in the region. The main research objective is to sociologically analyse the role played by religious institutions of Namghar and Sattria in shaping the social values of Assamese people and how these perform as centres of art, culture and folk traditions. The paper will attempt to locate neo-vaishnavism in the formation of a collective solidarity and a social order and religious system based on an Assamese identity which cuts across caste, class, ethnicity and faith. It will also look at the impact of Brahmanical ideology in the neo-Vaishnava faith after the death of Sankardeva and its further division into four sub-sects based on differences in beliefs and methods of worship. The methodology adopted for this study mostly revolves around qualitative methods using secondary data collection including books, journals, research articles and archival resources. The paper is significant

because it explores Neo-Vaishnavism as a living tradition in Assam and examines how Hinduism in Assam is practiced and performed differently from its manifestations in mainland India.

Keywords- Neo-Vaishnavism, Srimanta Sankardeva, Egalitarianism, Namghar, Sattra, Hinduism.

Introduction

The Neo-Vaishnavite movement in Assam, pioneered by Srimanta Sankardeva in the 15th and 16th centuries, was a religious and cultural reform movement that played a transformative role in Assamese society. Rooted in the broader Bhakti movement of India, Neo-Vaishnavism, also known as 'Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma,' emerged as a response to the rigid caste divisions and ritualistic orthodoxy prevalent at the time. This philosophical thought mainly follows the religious teachings of Lord Krishna (Sarma, 1996). Sankardeva was born in a place called Alipukhuri, a place close to Bardowa in Nagaon district of Assam. Sankardeva's teachings emphasized monotheism, social inclusivity, and devotion through chanting (Naam), rejecting idol worship and ritual sacrifices. This movement not only redefined religious practices but also profoundly impacted Assamese social structures, literature, art, and identity formation. During the fifteenth and sixteenth century, Neo- Vaishnavism had brought a large spectrum of changes in almost all aspects of life including socio-cultural and religious dimensions. It is well said in Bhagavata-purana and Gita that Lord Vishnu from time to time assumes incarnations in various forms to redeem the world and to graze his devotees. One such incarnation is Narayana. When a devotee completely surrenders his/her mind, body and ego in the feet of omnipotent Lord Krishna, then it is called as Eksarana (Borah, 2016). Nama, which comes under the act 'Eksarana-nam-dharma' is nothing but the recitation and singing of the glorious acts of Lord Krishna. Moreover, this can appropriately be termed as Nam-dharma. This Neo-Vaishnavite movement is a landmark change which has entirely altered the socio-cultural tradition prevailed in the Assamese society. There are several key aspects of this movement which is yet to be explored and learned. This paper traces the historical evolution of Neo-Vaishnavism, examines the role of its key institutions, and analyzes its socio-cultural influence on Assam.

In this system, there is an important aspect known as Sarana. The word Sarana derived from the Sanskrit root 'sr', literally means shelter or refuge, protection etc. and hence eka sarana in Mahapurusiya system means taking absolute shelter or refuge in one God, i.e. Vishnu-Krishna. In 'Sarana' system, the devotees can maintain direct communications with the lord without the help of anybody. In this system, there is no any system of caste or class. Sankardeva specifically emphasised on personal cleanliness—physical, mental and spiritual. Sankardeva gave prime emphasis on recitation or chanting of the holy names of the deity. In the initiation process, he introduced four elements i.e., Guru, Deva, Nama and Bhakat which are devotionally known as 'Icari Bastu'. The neo- Vaishnavite movement of Sankardeva ushered an era of wide culture comprising of music, dance and painting. He was not only an expert in handling the pen but also in singing, dancing and enacting what he composed. Through this, he spread his views on Vaishnavism and he advised his followers not to exhibit any aggression towards the adherents of other Creeds and said, "Parara Dharmmaka Nihimsibā Kādacit", (Sharma, 2011) (Never ever bear hatred towards others' religions). Sankardeva thus brought a great social reform by spreading secular ideas. It was because of the formative movement of Sankardeva that the stigma of casteism and untouchability could not attain such criminal proportion in Assam as prevailed in other parts of India till date.

Methodology

The research methodology section deals with a detailed description of the research procedure for collecting reliable data to meet with objectives. Therefore, the methodology adopted for this study will mostly revolve around qualitative methods using secondary data collection including books, journals, research articles and archival resources. A historical sociology approach is being adopted for writing this paper. The reliance on secondary resources is basically due to the nature of the study which is historical in nature and hence archival material becomes very important for such research.

Historical Evolution and Growth of Neo-Vaishnavism in Assam

The Neo-Vaishnavite movement in Assam traces its origins to the broader Bhakti movement that swept across India between the 12th and 17th centuries. This pan-Indian movement emphasized personal devotion (bhakti) over ritualistic and caste-based practices, promoting a direct connection between the devotee and the divine (Neog, 1980). In Assam, this movement took a distinctive form under Srimanta Sankardeva (1449–1568), who introduced *Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma*, a monotheistic faith centered on the devotion to Lord Krishna through prayer, congregational chanting (*naam*), and moral discipline.

Before the emergence of Neo-Vaishnavism, Assam was a region of diverse religious traditions, including Hinduism (Shaivism, Shaktism, and Tantrism), indigenous animistic beliefs, and Buddhism. The society was heavily influenced by Brahmanical orthodoxy, which upheld strict caste hierarchies and ritualistic practices such as animal sacrifice in temples (Sarma, 1966). The predominance of Shaktism and Tantric practices, particularly among the ruling classes, created a society where religious rituals were often elaborate and exclusionary. In this socio-religious context, Sankardeva's teachings emerged as a revolutionary force advocating for an egalitarian and accessible religious order (Goswami, 2012).

Born in 1449 in the Nagaon district of Assam, Sankardeva was exposed to Brahmanical learning early in life. However, his religious outlook changed significantly after an extensive pilgrimage across India, during which he encountered different Vaishnavite traditions in places like Puri, Vrindavan, and Dwarka (Neog, 1980). These travels played a crucial role in shaping his monotheistic vision and become the basis of his Neo-Vaishnavite philosophy.

On returning to Assam, Sankardeva formally began propagating *Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma* in the early 16th century. His teachings rejected elaborate Brahmanical rituals, idol worship, and caste-based restrictions, instead promoting devotion through *Naam-Kirtan* (chanting of God's name) and congregational worship in community spaces known as *Namghars* (Borah, 2016).

One of Sankardeva's key contributions was his use of Assamese language and literature to spread his teachings. He composed devotional songs (*Borgeets*), religious plays (*Ankiya Nat*), and translated Sanskrit texts such as the *Bhagavata Purana* into Assamese, making religious knowledge accessible to the common people (Sarmah, 2025). These efforts democratized religious practices, allowing non-Brahmins and marginalized communities to actively participate in spiritual life.

Sankardeva's most trusted disciple, Madhavdeva (1489–1596), played a crucial role in consolidating and expanding the movement. After Sankardeva's death, Madhavdeva continued his teacher's mission, further systematizing the philosophy and institutionalizing *Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma* through the establishment of *Sattras* (monastic centers) and *Namghars*. The *Sattras* became centers of religious instruction, artistic development, and social organization, ensuring the longevity of the movement (Sarma, 1966).

During this period, Neo-Vaishnavism gained substantial influence across Assam, attracting both commoners and nobility. The Ahom rulers, initially skeptical of the movement, later extended patronage to it, allowing it to flourish (Das & Saikia, 2020).

Despite its growing influence, the movement faced resistance from orthodox Brahmins and followers of Shakta traditions, who viewed the ideology and principles of Neo-Vaishnavism as a direct challenge to their authority. Over time, elements of Brahmanical influence crept into Neo-Vaishnavism, leading to the eventual division of the movement into four sub-sects—Brahma Sanghati, Purusha Sanghati, Nika Sanghati, and Kala Sanghati. Each of these sub-sects differed in their approach to worship, priestly roles, and ritual practices, reflecting the gradual assimilation of Brahmanical traditions (Neog, 1980).

During British rule in Assam, Neo-Vaishnavism experienced a revival as part of broader socio-cultural reforms. Scholars and social reformers like Anandaram Dhekial Phukan and Hemchandra Barua highlighted its role in shaping Assamese identity and resisting colonial

cultural impositions (Neog, 1980). The *Sattras* and *Namghars* continued to serve as community spaces, preserving Assamese folk traditions, music, and literary heritage.

In the 20th century, the movement influenced the Assam Agitation (1979–1985) and other socio-political movements, reinforcing Assamese cultural nationalism (Borah, 2016). Today, Neo-Vaishnavism remains an essential part of Assamese religious and cultural life, influencing everything from festivals to performing arts and social organization.

Institutional Role of Sattras and Namghars in Neo-Vaishnavism

One of the most significant contributions of Neo-Vaishnavism to Assamese society was the establishment of two key religious and socio-cultural institutions: the *Sattras* (monastic institution) and the *Namghar* (community prayer hall). These institutions have played a crucial role in preserving and propagating the Neo-Vaishnavite faith, shaping Assamese identity, and fostering social cohesion. The *Sattras* system, founded by Srimanta Sankardeva and further institutionalized by his disciple Madhavdeva, serves as a center for religious education, art, and culture, while the *Namghars* function as a grassroots-level communal space for worship and decision-making (Sarma, 1966). The evolution and impact of these institutions can be understood through the following aspects:

The *Sattras* are monastic institutions that serve as the central administrative and religious centers of the Neo-Vaishnavite movement. They function as hubs of religious teaching, literary and artistic development, and community organization. The first *Sattras* were established by Sankardeva at Belguri, near the Brahmaputra River, which later moved to Barpeta and other regions under the guidance of Madhavdeva (Neog, 1980). Over time, numerous *Sattras* were founded across Assam, each functioning as a self-sufficient religious institution.

A *Sattras* is traditionally led by a *Sattradhikar* (head monk), who oversees religious activities, education, and administrative duties. Other key members include: Bhakats (monastic disciples): Celibate monks who dedicate their lives to the teachings of Sankardeva, Deka

Bhakats (junior monks): Young initiates who undergo religious training. Mahantas and Pathaks: Scholars and preachers responsible for spreading Neo-Vaishnavite ideology.

Each *Sattras* functions as an autonomous institution, governing itself while following the broad principles of *Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma* (Neog, 1980). While some *Sattras* strictly maintain celibacy, others allow family life among their adherents.

The *Sattras* serve as centers of religious learning, where followers are taught Neo-Vaishnavite scriptures, *Borgeets* (devotional songs), and *Naam-Kirtan* (congregational chanting). The teachings emphasize devotion to Lord Krishna, ethical living, and social service (Das & Saikia, 2020). The study of texts such as *Kirtan-Ghosa* (a religious scripture composed by Sankardeva) and the *Bhagavata Purana* forms a core part of the monastic education.

Additionally, the *Sattras* play a vital role in preserving and transmitting Assamese literature and performing arts. They have been instrumental in the development of:

- **Bhaona (religious theatre):** A dramatic form introduced by Sankardeva to narrate stories from the *Bhagavata Purana*.
- **Ankiya Naat (one-act plays):** Devotional plays that blend Sanskrit and vernacular Assamese traditions.
- **Sattriya dance:** A classical dance form evolved within *Sattras*, now recognized as one of the eight classical dance forms of India.

The *Sattras* have historically functioned as agents of social reform, promoting values of equality and discouraging caste-based discrimination. They have provided shelter and education to people from different social backgrounds, ensuring the integration of marginalized communities into the mainstream religious and cultural life of Assam (Borah, 2016).

The *Namghar* (literally “House of Naam” or “House of Prayer”) is the grassroots-level institution of Neo-Vaishnavism. Unlike the *Sattras*, which function as centralized religious institutions, *Namghars* are decentralized community spaces present in almost every Assamese

village and town (Sharma, 2011). They serve as centers of religious worship, social interaction, and local governance.

A typical *Namghar* consists of a simple prayer hall with a raised platform (locally known as the *Manikut*), where the sacred scripture (*Bhagavata Purana*) is placed. It does not contain idols or images, in accordance with the anti-idolatri principles of Neo-Vaishnavism (Goswami, 2012). The *Namghar* is open to people of all castes and communities, reflecting Sankardeva's emphasis on social inclusivity.

The primary functions of a *Namghar* include:

- **Naam-Kirtan (communal chanting):** Regular prayer sessions involve collective chanting of Lord Krishna's name.
- **Religious festivals:** Celebrations such as *Janmashtami*, *Raas-Leela*, and *Dol Jatra* (Holi) are held in the *Namghars*.
- **Cultural performances:** *Bhaona* performances and musical gatherings often take place in *Namghars*.
- **Local dispute resolution:** The *Namghar* often acts as a local panchayat, where village elders and respected members mediate conflicts and make community decisions (Nath, 2020).

The *Namghar* serves as a unifying space that fosters community participation across caste and economic divisions. In contrast to Brahmanical temples, which traditionally restrict access to lower-caste individuals, the *Namghar* is open to all, reinforcing the democratic principles of Neo-Vaishnavism (Das & Saikia, 2020).

During the medieval period, *Namghars* played a crucial role in countering Brahmanical orthodoxy by providing a space where people could worship without the mediation of priests (Sarma, 1966). This was a revolutionary change that empowered the lower castes and promoted direct engagement with religious practices.

In contemporary Assam, *Namghars* continue to serve as important centers for community interactions and religious discourse. However, modern challenges such as urbanization, decreasing participation, and sectarian divisions among different *Namghars* have led to concerns about their long-term sustainability (Nath, 2020).

Formation of Assamese Identity Through Neo-Vaishnavism

The Neo-Vaishnavite movement played a pivotal role in shaping Assamese identity by fostering cultural unity, social cohesion, and a distinct religious consciousness. Prior to the movement, Assamese society was fragmented along caste, ethnic, and regional lines, with Brahmanical Hinduism, Shaktism, and indigenous animistic traditions coexisting but often creating hierarchical divisions (Neog, 1980). Srimanta Sankardeva's *Eka-Sarana-Naam-Dharma* provided a unifying religious framework that transcended these divisions, allowing diverse communities to integrate under a common spiritual and cultural ethos. From a sociological standpoint, this process can be understood through the lens of Durkheim's theory of collective consciousness, which posits that shared beliefs and rituals strengthen social solidarity (Durkheim, 1912).

One of the most significant ways Neo-Vaishnavism contributed to Assamese identity was through the establishment of *Namghars* and *Sattras*. These institutions became cultural and religious centers where people of all backgrounds could participate in collective worship, breaking traditional caste barriers (Borah, 2016). In Weber's notion of charismatic authority (Weber, 1978), religious leadership is able to reshape social structures by offering new forms of legitimacy and participation. The figures of Sankardeva and Madhavdeva exerted significant influence in the society through their charismatic authority to legitimize new forms of social control and led to the emergence of a new Assamese social structure. Unlike Brahmanical temples, which were often exclusive to higher castes, *Namghars* promoted an inclusive spiritual space, reinforcing a shared Assamese consciousness promoting structural integration and reinforcing social capital (Bourdieu, 1986) among Assamese communities (Borah, 2016).

Language and literature also played a crucial role in this identity formation. Sankardeva's use of the Assamese language in religious texts, dramas (*Ankiya Naat*), and devotional songs (*Borgeets*) made spiritual knowledge accessible to the masses and established Assamese as a literary and cultural medium. This not only standardized Assamese as a linguistic identity but also differentiated it from Sanskrit-dominated religious traditions in mainland India.

The artistic expressions associated with Neo-Vaishnavism, including Bhaona (ritual theatre) and Sattriya dance, further exemplify the ways cultural practices became carriers of collective identity (Das & Saikia, 2020). These performative traditions embedded in devotion to Krishna became emblematic of Assamese heritage and pride, creating what Clifford Geertz (1973) refers to as “webs of significance”—cultural meanings through which social groups define themselves. The ritual enactments fostered emotional solidarity and collective memory, strengthening community bonds across caste and ethnic lines.

Importantly, the movement's influence extended into everyday life practices—rituals, festivals, dietary norms, and kinship networks thus effectively shaping the moral and social fabric of Assamese society. The erosion of rigid caste barriers, while incomplete, signified a shift towards a more integrative social structure. From a functionalist sociological perspective, the movement served as a mechanism for social regulation and moral guidance, enabling communities to navigate modernity while preserving cultural continuity.

In essence, Neo-Vaishnavism provided Assam with a religious, linguistic, and cultural identity that continues to define its society today. It unified diverse communities, standardized the Assamese language, and created a distinct socio-religious fabric that remains integral to Assamese self-perception.

Brahmanical Influence and Sectarian Divisions in Neo-Vaishnavism

The Neo-Vaishnavite movement in Assam, founded by Srimanta Sankardeva in the 15th and 16th centuries, initially sought to establish an egalitarian religious order that rejected ritualistic orthodoxy, and caste-based hierarchies. However, over time, Brahmanical influences

began to seep into the movement, leading to sectarian divisions and internal conflicts that reshaped its practices and institutional structures (Neog, 1980). This transformation can be understood through two key processes: the gradual incorporation of Brahmanical elements and the formation of distinct sects within Neo-Vaishnavism.

During Sankardeva's lifetime, his teachings were rooted in a strict monotheistic devotion to Krishna, with an emphasis on congregational chanting (*Naam-Kirtan*) and direct communion with the divine, eliminating the need for intermediaries such as priests (Borah, 2016). However, following his death, his successor Madhavdeva continued the mission but faced increasing resistance from Brahmanical orthodoxy, which sought to reassert its control over religious affairs.

After Srimanta Sankardeva's death, his religious tradition split into four sanghatis (sub-sects) due to leadership disputes. Each group interpreted Sankardeva's teachings differently, particularly in terms of idol worship, priestly hierarchy, and monastic traditions. Though Sankardeva appointed Madhabdeva as his successor, followers of Damodardev and Haridev rejected his leadership, forming the **Brahma Sanghati**, which reintroduced Brahminical elements, allowed Vedic rituals, and emphasized idol worship, particularly Vishnu, Krishna, and Rama. The **Purush Sanghati**, led by Sankardeva's grandsons Purushottam Thakur and Chaturbhuj Thakur, focused on Naam (chanting) while permitting some Brahminical rites and idol worship. The **Nika Sanghati**, initiated by Mathuradas, Badala Padma Ata, and Kesava Ata, emphasized sat-sanga (true association) and followed strict purity codes. It strictly prohibited idol worship and held Madhabdeva in high regard. The **Kala Sanghati**, founded by Gopal Ata, emphasized the Guru as the embodiment of Deva. It attracted many tribal and socially marginalized groups, gaining the largest following. Some of its followers later led the Moamoria rebellion against the Ahom monarchy.

The impact of such divisions and entry of Brahmanism was the immediate loss of egalitarian values. While Sankardeva's original vision emphasized social equality, some factions, particularly Brahma Sanghati, began incorporating Brahmanical hierarchical structures, reintroducing caste-based restrictions (Goswami, 2012).

Despite these challenges, Neo-Vaishnavism remains deeply ingrained in Assamese society. The sectarian divisions, while significant, have not diminished its cultural impact, and the movement continues to play a vital role in shaping Assamese identity and spirituality. Despite divisions, all sects contributed to Assamese literature, art, and cultural identity. The performance arts of *Bhaona* (religious theatre) and *Sattriya* dance continued to flourish across sectarian lines, ensuring the survival of Neo-Vaishnavism as a living tradition.

Conclusion

The Neo-Vaishnavite movement, pioneered by Srimanta Sankardeva, has played an instrumental role in shaping the religious, cultural, and social fabric of Assam. Neo-Vaishnavism redefined Assamese religious and social structures, fostering an inclusive identity while enriching cultural traditions. Through the establishment of ‘Sattras’ and ‘Namghars’, Neo-Vaishnavism provided not just spiritual guidance but also served as an institution for social reform, artistic expression, and community organization. These institutions continue to function as centers of Assamese identity and heritage, fostering unity across diverse social groups. The movement’s influence on literature, performing arts, and social cohesion ensures that it remains a defining feature of Assamese cultural and religious life. The use of Assamese in religious texts, devotional songs (*Borgeets*), and dramatic performances (*Ankiya Naat* and *Bhaona*) helped standardize and strengthen the linguistic identity of Assam. The movement’s artistic expressions, particularly ‘Sattriya’ dance, have gained national and global recognition, ensuring its continued cultural relevance. However, the movement has also undergone transformations and challenges over time. The influence of Brahmanical traditions led to sectarian divisions within Neo-Vaishnavism, creating different ‘Sanghatis’ that varied in their adherence to Sankardeva’s original principles. Modern challenges such as urbanization, declining participation in monastic life, and conflicts over land and leadership have raised concerns about the sustainability of ‘Sattras’ and ‘Namghars’. Despite these challenges, efforts to revive traditional practices and adapt them to contemporary needs have kept the movement relevant. The dynamic interplay

between tradition and modernity allows Neo-Vaishnavism to remain relevant even in contemporary times.

Neo-Vaishnavism remains an enduring force in Assamese society. Its legacy of devotion, inclusivity, and cultural vibrancy continues to shape Assamese identity, ensuring that Sankardeva's teachings remain a guiding light for future generations.

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